
PISA simulations at PHENIX

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Abstract

This document outlines the procedure for generating, executing and analyzing simulation data using PISA within the PHENIX framework.

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1 Introduction

PISA is the PHENIX simulation software package based on the GEANT3 libraries. The output of the PISA package is a "hits file" which is processed by software which runs in the Fun4All OffLine system. The first stage in the processing is the detector response modules for all the detector subsystems. In the detector response module software, information obtained from the GEANT particle tracking through each detector subsystem is converted into simulated detector signals. These simulated signals are much like the real detector signals which appear on the real data PRDFs obtained by the OnLine system while the PHENIX experiment is taking data. Thereafter, these simulated detector signals are processed by the same software which reconstructs the real data files into useful physics information suitable for analysis software.¹

2 Setting up PISA

It is recommended that PISA be run in a separate directory. In order to get started, it must be kept in mind that the PISA set-up varies from run-to-run.

```
mkdir pisa
cd pisa
/afs/rhic.bnl.gov/phenix/PHENIX_LIB/simulation/run14/pisaLinker.csh
```

In this case, PISA is initialized to the Run 14 geometry.

The following 'READ-only' files are created in the directory.

- `flukaaf.dat`
PISA/FLUKA configuration file.
- `Sim3D++.root`
Magnetic field configuration file.
- `gffgo.dat`
PISA output format configuration.
- `phnx_full_hbd.par`
Detector configuration file with full HBD. This corresponds to the detector setup for the first part of the run7 data taking.
- `xsneut95.dat`
PISA/GEANT neutron tracking configuration.
- `phnx.par`
Current detector configuration file.

Some editable files are also created.

¹It is not advisable to work in the home directory due to space restrictions. Hence, once the PHENIX account is set up, please request for space on the working group disk (e.g. PLHF).

- `event.par`

PISA event generation configuration file. This may not be edited unless you want to use the PISA build-in vertex position generation capability

- `glogon.kumac`

PISA/GEANT logon macro. This file contains the various commands passed to PISA for processing, including some configuration variables, the type of input file, and the event processing command. It can be edited to change the PISA input file and/or input file format as well as the number of events to process.

- `pisa.input`

PISA startup input arguments.

- `pisa.kumac`

Main PISA configuration file. It allows to select the sign and scale of the magnetic field, which processes are enabled/disabled when tracking the particles through matter, and which detectors are enabled/disabled in the simulations.

In order to convert PISA output to DST files, some more codes are required.

```
/afs/rhic.bnl.gov/phenix/PHENIX_LIB/simulation/run14/pisaLinker.csh  
/afs/rhic.bnl.gov/phenix/PHENIX_LIB/simulation/run14/pisaToDSTLinker.csh
```

A number of calibration files are also linked to in the process.

3 Working examples

In order to start with a working example, we would use the following the setup from the following directory

```
/home/roli/pisa_tutorial
```

on HPSS. It can be retrieved by executing

```
hsi  
get /home/roli/pisa_tutorial  
exit  
tar -xvf pisa_tutorial
```

3.1 Simulations using OSCAR text file

In order to begin simulations, a toy code is needed to generate a text file in OSCAR format.

This can be done using the code:

```
void make_single_pi0(int nevt) {  
  
    gRandom = new TRandom3(0);  
    ofstream fout( "oscar.txt" );
```

```

int Npart_per_event = 1;

float mpi0 = 0.1349766; //GeV

for(int j = 0; j < nevt; j++){
  fout << 0 << " " << Npart_per_event << " " << endl;

  float zvertex = gRandom->Rndm() * pow(10,13); //cm to fm

  for(int i= 0; i < Npart_per_event; i++){
    float phi = gRandom->Rndm()*TMath::TwoPi(); //pi [0,2pi]
    float eta = gRandom->Rndm()*1.0-0.5; //eta [-0.5,0.5]
    float pt = 0.4 + 9.6*gRandom->Rndm(); //pt[0.4,10]

    float px = pt*TMath::Cos(phi);
    float py = pt*TMath::Sin(phi);
    float pz = pt*TMath::SinH(eta);
    float E = TMath::Sqrt(px*px+py*py+pz*pz+mpi0*mpi0);

    fout << i << " " << 111 << " " << 0 << " " << px << " " << py << " " << pz
    << " " << E << " " << mpi0 << " " << 0 << " " << 0 << " " << zvertex
    << " " << 0 << endl;
  }//End of particle

  fout << "0 0" << endl;

} //End of events

fout.close();
}

```

In the pisa directory, open **glogon.kumac**. If you are output for the pythia events in oscar format then change line 1 to:

```
text_file oscar.txt -1 40
```

Here 40 is the maximum number of particles processed in the event.

Here is a sample bash script to run the simulation.

```

#!/bin/sh

export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$LD_LIBRARY_PATH:/gpfs/mnt/gpfs02/phenix/plhf/plhf3/
nnovitzk/mazsi_Test/ccnt/source/emc-evaluation/build/.libs/;
PATH_TO_YOUR_INSTALL_DIRECTORY
export INSTALL=PATH_TO_YOUR_INSTALL_DIRECTORY
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$INSTALL/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
export TSEARCHPATH=PATH_TO_YOUR_INSTALL_DIRECTORY

mkdir temp
cd temp

```

```

NEVT=100 #Number of events

# Copy oscar file generating macro and pisa code
cp -r PATH_TO_FOLDER/make_single_pi0.C .
cp -r PATH_TO_FOLDER/pisa .

echo "=====  

root -l -b -q 'make_single_pi0.C('$NEVT')'  

mv oscar.txt pisa

echo "=====  

cd pisa  

sed -i '2s/./ptrig '$NEVT'/' glogon.kumac

pisa < pisa.input  

root -b -q -l pisaToDST.C

mv dst_out.root ../..

cd ../..
rm -r temp

```

3.2 Simulations using event generator (Pythia)

Following steps are need in order to first setup a PYTHIA environment within PHENIX.

- Download the pythia files:

```
cvs checkout event_gen/src/PHPythia
```

- To compile the code, run:

```
cd /event_gen/src/PHPythia/  

./autogen.sh --prefix=$MYINSTALL  

make install
```

- To generate some events using the base settings:

```
cd event_gen/src/PHPythia/macros  

root -b -q 'phpythia.C(1000)''
```

where 1000 is the number of events to generate.

By default pythia will put the events into a root file. In case you prefer oscar format then, in **phpythia.C** comment out the lines:

```

// DST output manager
TString OUTPUT = outputname;
Fun4AllDstOutputManager *dst_output_mgr = new
Fun4AllDstOutputManager("PHPYTHIA",OUTPUT.Data());
dst_output_mgr->AddNode("Sync");
dst_output_mgr->AddNode("PHPythiaHeader");
dst_output_mgr->AddNode("PHPythia");
se->registerOutputManager(dst_output_mgr);

```

and uncomment the lines:

```

// OSCAR output manager
// with following output manager, one can write the PHPythia output in an
oscar formatted output text file

PHPyOscarOutputManager *oscar_manager = new
PHPyOscarOutputManager( "OSCAR", oscar_outputname );
se->registerOutputManager(oscar_manager);

```

The default output file name for ROOT output is **phpythia.root** and for oscar output is **oscar.txt**.

To run the events through PISA, copy the output to the PISA directory. Some changes need to be made to the editable files in pisa. In the pisa directory, open **glogon.kumac**. If you are output for the pythia events in oscar format then change line 1 to:

```
text_file oscar.txt -1 500
```

If the output is in ROOT format then change line 1 to:

```
phpythia 500 phpythia.root
```

Note: In this 500 is the max number of particles in each subevent. If there are 700 particles produced in a pythia event then PISA would separate this into a 500 particle subevent and 200 particle subevent. Pythia usually only produces around 100-200 particles in each event so there will only be one subevent for each event

Change the second argument in line 4 to the number of generated events, e.g. for 1000 events it would read:

```
ptrig 1000
```

Finally to run PISA use commands:

```

pisa<pisa.input
root -b -q -l pisaToDST.C

```

The default output file name is

```
dst_out.root
```

Here is a sample bash script to automate this:

```

#!/bin/sh
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$LD_LIBRARY_PATH:/gpfs/mnt/gpfs02/phenix/plhf/plhf3/
nnovitzk/mazsi_Test/ccnt/source/emc-evaluation/build/.libs/:
PATH_TO_YOUR_INSTALL_DIRECTORY
export INSTALL=PATH_TO_YOUR_INSTALL_DIRECTORY
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$INSTALL/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
export TSEARCHPATH=PATH_TO_YOUR_INSTALL_DIRECTORY

mkdir temp
cd temp

NEVT=10 #Number of events per batch

# Copy pythia and pisa code
cp -r PATH_TO_FOLDER/event_gen/src/PHPythia/macros .
cp -r PATH_TO_FOLDER/pisa .

echo "=====  

cd macros
root -l -b -q 'phpythia.C('$NEVT')'
mv oscar.txt ../pisa

echo "=====  

cd ../pisa
sed -i '4s/./ptrig '$NEVT'' glogon.kumac
pisa<pisa.input
root -b -q -l pisaToDST.C
mv dst_out.root ../..
cd ../..
rm -r temp

```